

A Descriptive Study to Assess Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Ill-Effects of Substance Abuse among B.Sc. Nursing 1st Year & GNM 1st Year Students of Selected Nursing College in Greater Noida (U.P.)

Ankita Chhikara,¹

Nursing Lecturer Medical Surgical Nursing Department
Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University Knowledge Park-III,
Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh-201306

Ajay Verma,²

Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University, Knowledge Park-III,
Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh-201306

Ramandeep Kaur³,

Sharda School of Nursing Science and Research, Sharda University,
Knowledge Park-III,
Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh-201306
Corresponding Author

Abstract:- Substance abuse, also known as drug abuse, is a patterned use of drug in which the user consumes the substances in the amounts or which methods which are harmful to themselves or others, and is form of substance -related disorder.¹ **Aim:** The study's aim was to assess knowledge and attitude regarding ill-effects of substance abuse among B.Sc. Nursing 1st year & GNM 1st year students of selected Nursing College. **Methodology:** To assess knowledge and attitude regarding ill-effects of substance abuse among B.Sc. Nursing 1st year & GNM 1st year students of selected Nursing College, a descriptive design was utilised. The target population for the study was B.Sc. Nursing 1st year & GNM 1st year students. The analysis of the data was done using the study's aims and assumptions as the basis for the sample size of 60. Statistical Package EZR - Software version 2.4 was used to analyse the data. **Result:** Majority of 76.7% (46) students had average knowledge; 13.3% (8) students had good knowledge of substance abuse; 10.0% (6) had poor knowledge. Majority 85.0 % (51) of students have favourable attitude and 15.0% (9) have uncertain attitude level regarding the ill effects of substance abuse. **Conclusion:** As the findings of the present study revealed that education regarding ill effects of substance abuse is important for the nursing students as they are upcoming nurses and they can impart the knowledge to their adolescent patients on regular basis Nurses and nursing students should conduct research and workshop on ill effects of substance abuse.

Keywords:- Substance Abuse, Attitude, Knowledge, B.Sc. Nursing, G.N.M., Ill Effects, Substance Disorder.

I. INTRODUCTION

Drug abuse, usually referred to as substance abuse, is a pattern of drug use in which a person consistently consumes drugs in quantities or ways that are detrimental to them or others. It is a type of substance-related disorder.¹ The need to ingest or consume substances that are calming, stimulating, or euphoric has always existed in humans.² Substance abuse is a pattern of recurrent drug or alcohol use that frequently obstructs social or professional interactions.³ Abuse of drugs is now a widespread issue. Almost all countries have been impacted, albeit the severity and characteristics vary from region to region. At least 40 million people are thought to regularly abuse drugs or other substances worldwide. Drug addiction issues are concentrated in particular in India's metropolitan, semi-urban, and border regions. Adolescence is a time in a person's life when they are most vulnerable. During this time, psychological issues like curiosity, poor impulse control, running from reality, psychological anguish, and other issues led to an increase in susceptibility. The social variables, such as peer pressure, a hazy sense of identity, and internal or familial strife subject the youngster to drug use.⁴

➤ Objectives

- To assess the knowledge regarding the ill effects of substance abuse among the B.Sc. Nursing 1st year and GNM Nursing 1st year

- To assess the attitude regarding the ill effects of substance abuse among the B.Sc. Nursing 1st year and GNM Nursing 1st year
- To determine the correlation between the knowledge and attitude of B.Sc. Nursing students and GNM 1st year students

➤ *Research Hypothesis*

H₁: There will be a significant correlation between knowledge score and attitude score of B.Sc. Nursing 1st year students and GNM 1st year students

II. METHODOLOGY

A descriptive study design was used in this study to assess the knowledge attitude regarding ill-effects of substance abuse among B.Sc. Nursing 1st year students & G.N.M. 1st year students of selected Nursing College in Greater Noida (U.P). The research was carried out between May and June of 2019. By employing the convenient sampling strategy, the study's sample size was 60.

➤ *Ethical consideration:*

Obtained permission from

- Dean cum principal, School of Nursing Science and Research
- University ethical committee, Sharda University
- Head of institution, Principal of Prakash institute of Physiotherapy Rehabilitation and Allied Medical Science
- Participants consent will also be taken

➤ *Inclusion Criteria*

- Students of B.Sc. Nursing 1st year & G.N.M. 1st year of Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh
- Students of B.Sc. Nursing 1st year & G.N.M. 1st year of Prakash Institute, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh
- Students who are willing to participate
- Students who are present at the time of data collection

➤ *Exclusion Criteria*

- Students who are not present during the data collection
- Students who are not willing to participate

➤ *The study employed the following instruments to gather the data:*

- Demographic data is the first tool.
- Tool 2: Self-structured quiz on ill effects of substance abuse.
- Tool 3: Likert scale for assessing the attitude

III. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Using the statistical programme EZR - Version 2.4, descriptive and inferential statistics were utilised to analyse the data in accordance with the aims and hypotheses.

IV. RESULTS

The present study shows that, according to age, maximum number of subjects 36.7% (22) belongs to the age group of 20-22 years; 33.3% (20) belongs to the age group of 23- 25 years; 20% (12) belongs to the age group of 26-28 years; 10% (6) belongs to the age group of 17-19 years. As per residence, majority of the Respondents 86.9% (52) were from urban area and the minorities of the Respondents 13.1% (8) were from rural area As per 10+2 stream, most of respondents 43.3% (26) were from medical the stream; 40% (24) were from the commerce stream; 16.6% (10) were from arts stream. With regard to type of family, most of the Respondents 43.3% (26) were from the joint family; 40.1% (24) are from the nuclear family; 16.6% (10) were from the extended family. As per religion, most of the Respondents 46.7 (28) were Hindu; 20% (12) were Muslim; 20% (12) were Christian; 6.65% (4) were Sikh; 6.65% (4) were others. As per family monthly income, Maximum number of subjects 36.7% (22) were have monthly income 10.000-20.000 R.ps; 33.3% (20) were have monthly income 20.000-40.000 R.ps; 20% (12) were have monthly income >40.000; 10% (6) were have monthly income <10.000. As per source of information, Respondents 43.3% (26) had Heard Information about substance abuse thorough family & friends; 20% (12) from the internet and social sites; 20% (12) from the any other specify; 16.7% (10) from the Newspaper/TV. As per type of stay, most of the Respondents 43.3% (26) were staying in Hostel/Family; 40% (24) were staying with their friends; 16.7% (10) were staying with their family. As per the data obtained reveals that 13.3% (8) had poor knowledge, 76.7% (46) had average knowledge and 10.0% (8) had good knowledge regarding ill effects of the substance abuse.

The data reveals that majority 85.0% (51) of respondents have favorable attitude and 15.0% (9) have uncertain attitude level regarding the ill effects of substance abuse. The data reveals that there is no significant correlation between knowledge score and attitude score of the students. The Karl Pearson correlation obtained is $r=0.07$ and p value is 0.

Table 1 Percentage and frequency distribution of B.Sc. nursing 1st year and G.N.M. 1st year students according to the level of knowledge regarding the ill effects of substance abuse. (N=60)

Knowledge level	Frequency	Percentage
Poor	6	10.0 %
Average	46	76.7 %
Good	8	13.3 %
Total	60	100 %

Table 1 revealed that as per the data obtained reveals that 13.3% (8) had poor knowledge, 76.7% (46) had average knowledge and 10.0% (8) had good knowledge regarding ill effects of the substance abuse.

V. DISCUSSION

As per the data obtained reveals that 13.3% (8) had poor knowledge, 76.7% (46) had average knowledge and 10.0% (8) had good knowledge regarding ill effects of the substance abuse. The data reveals that majority 85.0% (51) of respondents have favourable attitude and 15.0% (9) have uncertain attitude level regarding the ill effects of substance abuse.

Students studying nursing should be well-versed on the negative impacts of substance abuse. The evolving idea of an enlarged position in nursing practice denotes shifting roles and responsibilities. Increased knowledge and competence are necessary for expanded practice to produce high-quality treatment. According to the results of the current study, nursing students should be educated about the negative effects of substance misuse because they will soon become nurses and will be able to regularly teach their patients who are adolescents this information. Research on the negative impacts of substance addiction should be done by nurses and nursing students, as well as workshops.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study can be generalized by applying it on large samples. An experimental study should be carried out to assess the effectiveness of planned teaching Programme on knowledge regarding ill effects of substance abuse among the B.Sc. Nursing 1st year and GNM 1st year students. Other interventions like psychoeducation or web based education can be used.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Volkow ND, et al. Loss of dopamine transporters in methamphetamine abusers recovers with protracted abstinence. *J Neurosci* 21(23):9414–9418, 2001.
- [2]. Wang G-J, et al. Partial recovery of brain metabolism in methamphetamine abusers after protracted abstinence. *Am J Psychiatry* 161(2):242–248, 2004.
- [3]. Woules T, LaGasse L, Sheridan J, Lester B. Maternal methamphetamine use during pregnancy and child outcome: what do we know? *N Z Med J* 117:U1180, 2004
- [4]. Petry NM, Peirce JM, Stitzer ML, Blaine J, Roll JM, Cohen A, Obert J, Killeen T, Saladin ME, Cowell M, Kirby KC, Sterling R, Royer-Malvestuto C, Hamilton J, Booth RE, Macdonald M, Liebert M, Rader L, Burns R, DiMaria J, Copersino M, Stabile PQ, Kolodner K, Li R. Effect of prize-based incentives on outcomes in stimulant abusers in outpatient psychosocial treatment programs: a national drug abuse treatment clinical trials network study. *Arch Gen Psychiatry* 62(10):1148–1156, 2005.